

Resistance of rice varieties to WBPH at Banswara, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Cross	Damage rating ^a	Reaction ^b
RPW6-18	IR8/Siam 9	7	S
Pusa 44-33	IR5901-2/IR8	9	HS
R35-2750	IR8JW1263	4	MR
RP825-28-7-1	Vijaya/PTB21	6	S
RP25-45-1-3	Vijaya/PTB21	5	MR
BR51-46-1-0-1	IR20/IR5-114-3	7	S
IR52	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071//IR206	5	MR
RP1670-1418-2208-1585	M63-83/Cauvery	8	HS
RAU72-9-20-1-1	IR8/IR12-178	4	MR
UPR239-151-1-1	Hamsa/IR24	7	S
UPR231-28-1-2	Ratna/YR13-89-11	5	MR
RP1898-6	Mettasanna/Rasi	5	MR
HKR 101	—	5	MR
RP2151-40-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	3	R
RP2151-21-22	IET4141/CR98-7216	4	MR
RP1831-36-1-4	Surekha/CR147-7369	1	R
RP1832-23-3-4	CR141-7404/Surekha	2	R
RR5 1-1	ARC6650/TNI//Mudgo/PTB 33	8	HS
RP2086-74-6-1	IET5854/IET6187	9	HS
CR314-5-10	—	8	HS
CR314-5-3	—	9	HS
RP2240-86-84	RP143-4/Phalguna	3	R
RP2240-153-151	RP143-4/Phalguna	5	MR
RP2246-72	Pusa 2-21/Surekha	6	S
HKP20	—	4	MR
AR26-5-3-5	Paizam/IR8	2	R
NRL-162	Jaya mutant/Bas. 370	6	S
SKL-17-67-11	W13400/W11216	6	S
Pusa 587-2-1	—	2	R
RNDR88-1-1	IR36/T21	3	R
UPR79-151	—	6	S
UPRS1-47	—	6	S
KD3-5-13	—	4	MR
RP9263-2256-2	Sona/ARC1154	5	MR
RP2263-2561-1	Sona/ARC1154	7	S
RP1686-616-1	IET3262/Dhaneswar	9	HS
RP2440-32-28	RP143-4/Phalguna	7	S
RP2240-142-139	RP143-4/Phalguna	7	S
RR52-1	CR188-10/Indira	9	HS
IR18348-36-3-3	IR5657-33-2-1/IR2061-465-1-5-5	3	R
BK79	—	6	S
BK190	—	7	S
BK398	—	5	MR
BK657	—	8	HS
Chambal	—	4	MR
BK770	—	5	MR
CR220-66	—	6	S
Ratna	—	8	HS
Jaya	—	9	HS
IR36	—	6	S

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Eight varieties scored resistant and 15 moderately resistant (see table). Eleven were highly susceptible. RP1831-36-1-4, RP1832-23-3-4, AR26-5-3-5. and Pusa 587-2-1 showed high resistance; Jaya, Pusa 44-33, CR314-5-3, RP1686-616-1, RR52-1, and RP2086-74-6-1 were highly susceptible. □

Pothana — a gall midge (GM) resistant variety for endemic areas of Andhra Pradesh

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Pothana (IR579/ W12708), recently released for GM endemic areas, is 90 cm tall and produces compact, dense panicles and long slender grains. The leaf margin and other plant parts are purple. It matures in 125 d during the monsoon and 135 d during the winter seasons. It is almost immune to GM attack and is tolerant of yellow stem borer.

In trials from 1982 to 1984, Pothana yielded an average 4.3 t/ha. Because GM incidence is high in the monsoon crop, the yield advantage in this season is spectacular. Among 64 varieties tested at 21 locations in 1981, Pothana ranked second with a grain yield of 4 t/ha. □

Evaluation for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We evaluated field resistance to BPH of 13 cultivars, including Jaya and Ratna

Field resistance of rice varieties to BPH in Cuttack, Orissa, India, 1983.

Variety	BPH no./hill at 90 DT	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)
OR131-13-13	11.4	86	4.9
IR13429-196-1-20	19.6	82	4.2
IR36	63.1	87	4.2
OR131-11	7.7	96	4.0
CR157-22-1900	32.9	91	4.0
IR1342-108-2-2-3	32.2	85	3.9
OR158-13-1	197.5	88	3.4
OR131-3-1	8.9	100	3.3
OR136-3	16.5	99	2.9
Ratna	217.6	82	2.6
Jaya	112.3	98	2.6
OR131-3-3	9.7	98	2.4
IR19661-364-1-2-3	9.4	96	2.0

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as susceptible checks, in the summer season in the Adaptive Research Centre, Barachana, Cuttack. Three-week-old seedlings were planted in 20-m² plots at 15 × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The BPH population was sampled from 20 hills/plot at 15-d intervals, starting from 45 d after transplanting (DT).

The BPH population did not exceed 8 individuals/hill until 60 DT; at 90 DT susceptible Ratna and Jaya had 218 and 112 BPH/hill. OR158-13-1 was highly susceptible with 198 BPH/hill. OR131-11 and OR131-13-13 had only 7.7 and 11.3 BPH/hill and yielded more than 4 t/ha (see table). □

New sources of resistance to gall midge (GM) and yellow stem borer (YSB)

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GM and YSB are serious pests of rice in the Northern Telangana region of Andhra Pradesh in both monsoon and winter seasons. We screened 97 varieties for resistance to natural infestations of YSB and GM.

Entries were planted in single 3-m-long rows; each row had 20 plants. GM incidence was recorded 50 d after transplanting; whitehead damage caused by YSB was recorded at harvest.

IET8340, IET8637, IET8797, RP1579-36-33, RP2091-272-3-4-8, RP2091-272-8-2-7, RP2434-24-1-2, Moirangpheu, Aganni, and W1263 had less than 5% GM and YSB damage. □

Screening for resistance to yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We screened 24 varieties for YSB resistance under natural infestation during 1984 kharif. Two 30-d-old

seedlings were transplanted/hill with 20 × 15-cm spacing in 3-m-long rows. TN1 was the susceptible check. Deadheart damage on 20 hills of each variety was recorded at 50 d after transplanting.

ARC5500, ARC6588, CO 18, RYT2908, W1263, ASD7, T7, RP2199-

115-2, ARC62 15, and Manoharsali scored resistant (0-5% deadhearts). RP2199-162-2 was moderately resistant (5.1-10% deadhearts). Other entries were susceptible (10.1-25% deadhearts) or highly susceptible (more than 25% deadhearts). □

Screening rice cultivars against rice whorl maggot (RWM)

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We screened 21 varieties against RWM *Hydrellia sasakii* in the 1986 multilocation trial. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The cross plot size was 8.325 m².

Seedlings were planted 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Affected leaves and unaffected leaves were counted from 5 random hills/plot.

At 25 d after transplanting, damage was 22-57% (see table). IR64 had 57% damage. Nineteen entries, with more than 25% damage, were considered highly susceptible. Only IR28128-45-2 and TNAUBPHR831293, with 25 and 22% damage, were classified moderately resistant. □

Varieties highly susceptible and moderately resistant to RWM. Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, 1986.

Variety	Cross combination	Leaf damage (%)
<i>Highly susceptible</i>		
IR64	IR5657-33-2-1/IR2061-465-1-5-5	57.3
ACM5	Jhona 349/IR28	56.6
IR62	ITB33/IR30/IR36	52.2
TKM9	TM7/IR8	52.1
ACM12	-	51.7
ACM11	Manila/IR8	50.7
ET7254	Triveni/CO 39	50.0
TNAUBPHR831305	T7/IR8	50.0
BG367-4 (AD 85003)	BG280-1*2/PTB33	45.5
ASD16	ADT31/CO 39	43.9
TNAU83152	PV2/IR36	42.0
KT7987	M63-83/Sarya	39.7
IET7988	N22/IR36	38.8
TNAU831520	PY2/IR36	34.8
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	36.0
ACM9	Selection from IR50	33.3
TNAUBPHR831305	T7/IR8	33.3
AS28883	TKM9/IR36	31.3
AS25370	ASDI/IRON297	29.5
<i>Moderately resistant</i>		
IR28128-45-2	IR36/IRIO154-23-3-3//IR9129-209-2-2-2-1	25.0
TNAUBPHR831293	T7/IR20	22.2

Modified seedbox screening test to identify field resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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In field screening for resistance to BPH at IRRI, some varieties are resistant in the field but susceptible at early seedling stage in the greenhouse. We modified the standard seedbox screening test